

FACTORS GOVERNING THE TENSILE STRENGTH OF BASALT FIBRE

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ABSTRACT

In this study, using basalt fibers produced by different manufacturers as the study subject. The basalt fibers were characterized by scanning electron microscope (SEM), atomic force microscopy (AFM), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) and Raman spectroscopy. The chemical composition of basalt fibers were determined by inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) and potassium dichromate titrimetric method. The mechanical properties of single fibers were investigated by tensile tests using XQ-1A fiber tensile tester. The influences of Al₂O₃ content, Al₂O₃/network former, Fe³⁺/ΣFe on the mechanical properties of basalt fibers were investigated in details. The results showed that layered structure unit, chain structure unit, island structure unit and Si-Al replacement unit are all existed in basalt fiber microstructure. Al₂O₃ content plays a key role in the mechanical properties of basalt fibers, followed by Fe³⁺/ΣFe. Fe³⁺/ΣFe destroyed the regular pattern of the chemical composition in microstructure.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced polymers (FRPs) have been extensively used as structural components in a variety of industries ranging from aeronautics and automotive to civil infrastructure owing to their high specific stiffness and strength as well as their outstanding fatigue performance [1]. High performance filaments, such as carbon fibers, glass fibers and ceramic fibers, are frequently used as the reinforcement of the composites [2]. Glass fiber has good mechanical properties, low weight, low cost and a relatively good interfacial adhesion to the matrix. In the production of glass fiber, boric oxide (B₂O₃) is used and easy to be volatilized, thus causes pollution to the environment. Meanwhile its recycling is not easy. Carbon fiber is used when there are more special and higher requirements, such as space technology, aircraft industry, military applications and sports. However, carbon fiber has higher cost than glass fiber and the adhesion between carbon fiber and the matrix is more difficult for its chemically inert surface [3].

Nowadays, environment-friendly and cost effective materials have recently been received considerable attention among human beings. Basalt fiber is a kind of sodium aluminosilicate fiber which mainly composed of the oxides of the elements such as Si, Al, Fe, Ca, Mg, Na, K, Ti and so on [4]. Basalt fiber is made from natural basalt rock, which is an environment-friendly natural material widely distributed on the earth and composed of various minerals. In the production of basalt fiber, the basalt is simply washed and then sent to be melted down, no additives are added to the melt, and no toxic substance are produced, which is in contrast with glass fiber production [5]. Moreover, basalt fiber can be discharged directly into the natural environment after being abandoned. Basalt fiber is colloquially known as the “twenty-first century nonpolluting green material”. It is well known that basalt fiber possesses many superior properties, such as outstanding mechanical properties, high chemical, sound and heat resistance, wide working temperature range, excellent electrical insulation performance, as well as being non-toxic and non-combustible [6, 7].

The application of basalt fiber in FRPs and the mechanical properties of the composites have been investigated in many recent studies. Kim et al. [8] examined the applicability of basalt fiber as

reinforcing materials in an epoxy matrix and analyzed the mechanical properties of basalt and glass fibers as a fiber reinforced composites. The results indicated that the strength of the basalt fibers was excellent compared to glass fibers. In addition, the mechanical properties of the basalt fiber-reinforced composites were higher than those of the glass fiber-reinforced materials. Manikandan et al. [9] developed unsaturated polyester-based polymer composites by reinforcing basalt fabric into an unsaturated polyester matrix using the hand layup technique at room temperature and studied the effect of surface modifications (NaOH & H₂SO₄) on mechanical properties, including tensile, shear and impact strengths. The results showed that the mechanical properties of basalt fiber reinforced composites are superior to glass fiber reinforced composites. It also confirmed the applicability of basalt fiber as a reinforcing agent in polymer composites.

At present, a large number of scientists pay attention to how to develop and utilize this new kind of fiber, as well as the development and application of basalt fiber reinforced composites.

However, the research on the characteristics of basalt fiber is lacking. One of the major issues concerning basalt fiber is that the measured strengths are significantly lower than their theoretical values. The strength of basalt fibers is influenced by the chemical composition, processing conditions and the presence of surface and internal defects that are created during manufacturing and handling [10]. Therefore, it is important to study the performance of basalt fibers and the influences of its chemical composition on the mechanical properties.

The purpose of this work was to study the microstructure of basalt fibers and the influences of Al₂O₃ content, Al₂O₃/network former, Fe³⁺/ΣFe on the mechanical properties of basalt fibers.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Basalt fibers with an average diameter of 13 μm were supplied by different manufacturers of China. The sizing on the surface of basalt fibers was repeatedly reflux washed with acetone in Soxhlet extractor for 72 h. All solvents and other reagents were purchased from commercial sources and used as received.

The morphology and topography of basalt fibers were characterized by scanning electron microscope (SEM) of Phenom XL (Phenom World, Netherlands) and atomic force microscopy (AFM) of Bruker Insight AFP (Germany). The molecular structures and chemical functional groups of samples were recorded by the Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) of Nicolet 6700 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, United States) and Raman spectroscopy of LabRAM HR800 (Horiba Jobin Yvon, France).

The basalt fibers were dissolved with hydrofluoric acid and perchloric acid. The chemical composition of basalt fibers was determined by inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) of VISTA-PRO CCD Simultaneous ICP-OES (United States). The content of Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺ in basalt fiber was determined with potassium dichromate titrimetric method using sodium diphenylamine sulfonate as indicator. The amount of oxides was calculated from the elementary composition.

The mechanical properties of single fibers were investigated by tensile tests using XQ-1A fiber tensile tester. The tests were executed according to the ASTM C1557-14 standard, with a gauge length of 25 mm and the crosshead speed of 2 mm/min. 30 specimens of each material were tested and the mean values and standard deviations of the tensile strength were calculated. The tensile strength distributions were analyzed using a two-parameter Weibull model.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Characterization of basalt fibers

The morphologies of basalt fibers surface before and after removing the sizing and cross-section are shown in Figure 1. The sizing on the surface of basalt fibers can be clearly seen in Figure 1(a), and it also has some solid particles attached. These particles may be some poorly soluble substances in the sizing, or may be the defects produced in the process of production. Therefore, the surface of fibers with the sizing is rough. After removing the sizing, the as-received basalt fibers in Figure 1(b) exhibit a smooth surface with an average diameter closed to 13 μm. The cross-section of the basalt fiber is

almost circular as shown in Figure 1(c), the fracture mode is brittle fracture.

Figure 1: SEM images of basalt fibers surface before (a) and after (b) removing the sizing and cross-section (c).

The morphology and topography of the basalt fibers before and after removing the sizing were further analyzed via the AFM as shown in Figure 2. The light yellow “islands” in the AFM height image of basalt fiber with sizing (Figure 2a) reflect a heterogeneous surface of the fibers due to the presence of the sizing. The roughness R_q and R_a values are 6.28 and 4.58 nm, respectively. The surface of de-sized basalt fiber is quite smooth with the R_q and R_a values of 2.35 and 1.80 nm, respectively. But it still can see a lot of “aiguilles” in the 3D AFM image (Figure 2b), which suggests the shape of the fibers is not perfectly cylindrical but it presents some imperfections [11].

Figure 2: AFM height images, section height images and 3D profile images of the surfaces of basalt fiber before (a) and after (b) removing the sizing.

Figure 3 shows the FT-IR spectra of basalt fibers without sizing. The peak at 3430 cm^{-1} and 1635 cm^{-1} are assigned to the hydrogen bonded O-H stretching vibration that can come either from water adsorbed on the fiber surface or from the silanol groups, -Si-OH. The peak at 996 cm^{-1} is ascribed to the stretching vibration of Si-O. The peak at 723 cm^{-1} is attributed to the stretching vibration of Si-O-Si and Si-Al. The peak at 452 cm^{-1} is attributed to the bending vibration of Si-O-Si (Al) in inosilicate [12, 13].

Figure 3: FT-IR spectra of basalt fibers without sizing.

Figure 4 shows the Raman spectroscopy of basalt fibers without sizing. The peak at 1031.3 cm^{-1} is attributed to the stretching vibration of Si-O with a non-bridge oxygen number of 1, which is mainly existed in $[\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5]^{2-}$. The peak at 964.3 cm^{-1} is related to the stretching vibration of Si-O with a non-bridge oxygen number of 2, which is mainly existed in $[\text{Si}_2\text{O}_6]^{4-}$. The peak at 772.5 cm^{-1} is attributed to the bending vibration of Al-O. The peak at 673.5 cm^{-1} is ascribed to the bending vibration of Si-O-Si, which is mainly existed in $[\text{SiO}_4]^{4-}$. The peak at 557.2 cm^{-1} is attributed to the stretching vibration of Si-O-Si or Al-O-Al. The peaks below 500 cm^{-1} are mostly caused by the vibration of alkali metal oxides and alkaline earth metal oxides [12-14]. In conclusion, layered structure unit, chain structure unit, island structure unit and Si-Al replacement unit are all existed in basalt fiber microstructure.

Figure 4: Raman spectroscopy of basalt fibers without sizing.

The chemical composition of investigated fibers is presented in Table 1. For the sake of convenience, the basalt fibers producing from different manufacturers are marked as BF-I, BF-II, BF-III, BF-IV, BF-V, BF-VI, BF-VII, respectively. It can be seen that the composition of the basalt fibers varies with its place of origin. Basalt fiber is mainly built up from SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , FeO , Fe_2O_3 , CaO , MgO , Na_2O , K_2O et al. The fiber is belonging to sodium aluminosilicate fiber. The basic properties of basalt fibers depend on their chemical composition and processing of production and SiO_2 is the fundamental component.

Sample	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	Na ₂ O	CaO	MgO	K ₂ O	FeO	TiO ₂	MnO	P ₂ O ₅
BF-I	54.95	13.30	7.04	7.33	6.54	3.50	3.26	2.52	0.85	0.42	0.29
BF-II	54.80	14.28	6.01	5.97	7.19	4.60	2.55	3.34	0.86	0.15	0.26
BF-III	50.80	14.40	5.56	6.32	7.92	4.47	2.23	5.25	2.16	0.23	0.68
BF-IV	49.73	14.79	3.91	7.27	9.43	5.73	1.21	6.09	1.40	0.29	0.16
BF-V	53.41	15.13	3.03	6.14	7.58	4.86	2.62	5.98	0.81	0.15	0.29
BF-VI	52.73	15.15	4.17	4.53	8.61	6.37	0.76	5.93	1.41	0.15	0.18
BF-VII	50.53	15.73	7.06	5.52	2.73	6.59	0.82	9.34	1.36	0.13	0.19

Table 1: Chemical composition of basalt fibers.

The connection of glass network structure is one of the key factors that affecting the monofilament tensile strength of basalt fibers. A tighter connection of glass network structure will lead to higher monofilament tensile strength. The connection of glass network structure is affected by the chemical composition of the basalt fibers [15]. In sodium aluminosilicate fibers, SiO₂ is a glass network former and [SiO₄]⁴⁻ tetrahedra is the basic structural unit. Al₂O₃ plays a dual role of glass network former and glass network modifier. Gutnikov et al. [16] indicated that, the behavior of Al₂O₃ depends on the ratio of $n(\text{Al}^{3+}):n(\text{R}^+/\text{R}^{2+})$ in the glass, R stands for alkali metals and alkaline earth metals: when $n(\text{Al}^{3+}):n(\text{R}^+/\text{R}^{2+}) < 1$, Al³⁺ is considered to occupy the central position of [AlO₄]⁵⁻ tetrahedron, thus, Al₂O₃ is acted as a glass network former; when $n(\text{Al}^{3+}):n(\text{R}^+/\text{R}^{2+}) > 1$, Al₂O₃ becomes a glass network modifier. The role of Fe₂O₃ depends on the redox state of iron. In oxidized iron-bearing silicate glasses ($\text{Fe}^{3+}/\Sigma\text{Fe} > 50\%$, where $\Sigma\text{Fe} = \text{Fe}^{2+} + \text{Fe}^{3+}$) Fe³⁺ is primarily in tetrahedral coordination and acted as a glass network former, whereas in very reduced iron-bearing silicate glasses ($\text{Fe}^{3+}/\Sigma\text{Fe} < 30\%$) Fe³⁺ is in octahedral coordination and acted as a glass network modifier [17, 18]. In addition, FeO, TiO₂, MgO, CaO, Na₂O, K₂O, P₂O₅ and MnO are glass network modifiers. In general, the glass network formers can increase the degree of polymerisation and make the glass network structure more closely connected, the glass network modifier can disrupt the glass network structure and decrease the degree of polymerisation also make it looser.

Figure 5: Characters of silicate configuration: framework silicate (a), (b) phyllosilicate, inosilicate (c), ring silicate (d), nesosilicate (e).

The structure of silicate is very complex, according to the connection type of $[\text{SiO}_4]^{4-}$ tetrahedral, it can be divided into framework silicate, phyllosilicate, inosilicate, ring silicate, nesosilicate. The degree of polymerisation gradually decreases in this order. In order to present the silicate structure more intuitively, the structure of different silicates and the structural change process are shown in Figure 5.

In general, the characteristic of the glass network structure can be described using the following parameters [14]:

R: the ratio of oxygen to silicon, it refers to the average number of oxygen ions per glass network former possessed;

Z: the coordination number of each glass network former, it is four co-ordinated for SiO_2 ;

X: the number of “non-bridging oxygen” in each glass network former;

Y: the number of “bridging oxygen” in each glass network former.

The relationship between R, Z, X and Y is as follows:

$$Z = X + Y \quad (1)$$

$$R = X + 1/2Y \quad (2)$$

The glass network structure parameters can be obtained from the chemical composition of basalt fibers, and the calculation results of the investigated basalt fibers are shown in Table 2. The values of R are all between 2.19 and 2.44, and the values of Y are all between 3.12 and 3.62, which is closed to the value of phyllosilicate and framework silicate. Therefore, it can be concluded that the network structure of all these investigated basalt fibers are tightly connected, take layered structure unit and framework structure unit as the main, chain structure unit, ring structure unit and group structure unit as the auxiliary.

Sample	R	X	Y
BF-I	2.19	0.38	3.62
BF-II	2.20	0.41	3.59
BF-III	2.28	0.55	3.45
BF-IV	2.44	0.88	3.12
BF-V	2.33	0.67	3.33
BF-VI	2.38	0.75	3.25
BF-VII	2.40	0.80	3.20

Table 2: Glass network structure parameters of the investigated basalt fibers.

The results of diameter measurements and tensile tests before and after removing the sizing can be seen in Table 3. All of the tested fibers had a rigid behavior, without plastic deformation. In addition, the failure methods of all basalt fibers were quite similar. The tensile strength was calculated using the following equations:

$$\sigma = \frac{P}{A} \quad (3)$$

where σ (MPa) is the monofilament tensile strength of basalt fiber; P (N) is the fracture load; A (mm^2) is the average cross-sectional area of the single fiber.

The monofilament tensile strength exhibited significant scattering. Therefore, the two-parameter Weibull model was adopted for the evaluation of strength distribution, in which the probability of failure P , of a fiber with length L failed at an applied strength σ is given by [10, 19]:

$$P = 1 - \exp \left[-\frac{L}{L_0} \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^m \right] \quad (4)$$

where m is the Weibull modulus (shape parameter); σ is the monofilament tensile strength tested at the gauge length L ; σ_0 is the characteristic fiber strength (scale parameter) at a gauge

length L_0 ; and L_0 is the largest fiber length that contains only one flaw. In general, L_0 is chosen to be unity for reasons of simplicity. Then by taking the natural logarithms of Eq. (4) and further rearrangement the following equation is derived:

$$\ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{1-P}\right)\right) = m \ln(\sigma) - m \ln(\sigma_0) + \ln(L) \quad (5)$$

Therefore, if $\ln(\sigma)$ is plotted versus $\ln\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{1-P}\right)\right)$ a straight line should appear, whose slope is the Weibull modulus, m , and the characteristic fiber strength σ_0 can be obtained from the intercept of the line. Usually the probability of fiber failures P is estimated by:

$$P = \frac{i}{n+1} \quad (6)$$

where n is the number of fibers that are effectively tested; i the rank of the data point, which is selected according to the following method: Firstly, all of the effectively tested tensile strength are arranged in the order of smallest to largest. Then, each tensile strength value corresponds to a sequence number, it is exactly i .

In order to avoid the influence of sizing on the mechanical properties of basalt fibers, all the mechanical properties we studied in the following were after the removal of the sizing.

Sample	Diameter (um)	Sizing			De-sizing		
		Tensile Strength (MPa)	Weibull Modulus	Weibull Strength (MPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Weibull Modulus	Weibull Strength (MPa)
BF-I	12.7±0.9	1420±390	3.9	3560	1220±330	3.9	3061
BF-II	12.2±0.7	1680±340	5.2	3362	1440±320	5.0	2969
BF-III	13.0±2.6	1910±320	6.4	3380	1630±290	5.8	3051
BF-IV	12.8±2.2	2080±320	6.7	3580	1690±270	6.5	2963
BF-V	12.5±0.9	2100±340	6.8	3611	1730±270	6.7	2988
BF-VI	13.0±0.7	2200±320	7.4	3612	1750±300	6.2	3170
BF-VII	12.2±0.8	2380±330	8.1	3727	1890±240	7.7	3040

Table 3: Results of fiber diameter measurements and tensile tests.

3.2 Factors affecting the mechanical properties of basalt fibers

3.2.1 Effect of Al_2O_3 content

The relationship between Al_2O_3 content and monofilament tensile strength of all the investigated basalt fibers is presented in Figure 6. The linear correlation coefficient (R^2) is 0.94 by fitting the data of Al_2O_3 content and tensile strength. As shown in Figure 6, the monofilament tensile strength of basalt fibers are growing linearly with the increasing of Al_2O_3 content. The main reason for the tensile strength increase brought about by the increase of Al_2O_3 content is that: (1) For all these seven kinds of basalt fibers, $n(Al^{3+}): n(R^+/R^{2+}) < 1$, Al^{3+} is considered to occupy the central position of $[AlO_4]^{5-}$ tetrahedron, Al_2O_3 is acted as a glass network former. When four coordinated Al^{3+} are introduced in the network of $[SiO_4]^{4-}$ tetrahedra, each Al^{3+} contributes only $3/2 O^{2-}$ and thus ties up half of a non-bridging oxygen present per R^+ or $1/2 R^{2+}$. The decrease in non-bridging oxygen increases the number of bridging oxygen and tetrahedra in the basalt glass network structure. Thus, an increase in three dimensional network formation by adding Al_2O_3 content brings about an increase in monofilament tensile strength [20]. (2) In the preparation process of basalt fibers, an increasing of Al_2O_3 percentage gives rise to a small increase of in melt viscosity, which inhibits defect generation during fiber drawing process [16]. The basalt fibers with fewer defects possess higher tensile strength.

Figure 6: Correlation of Al₂O₃ content and tensile strength of investigated basalt fibers.

Figure 7 shows the Weibull plots of monofilament tensile strength for basalt fibers produced by different manufacturers. A large variation of monofilament tensile strength at 25 mm gauge length is evident. It is widely accepted that the brittle fibers have internal and surface defects, which influence the strength. Weibull modulus is used to characterize the distribution of the strength and defect position of fibers. The larger Weibull modulus correspond to smaller discreteness values, thus indicate that the distribution of the strength and defect position of fibers is more homogeneous. The Weibull distribution parameters can be calculated by the linear regression method, and the regression coefficients R^2 were all close to unity for all the investigated basalt fibers, indicating the validity of the method used.

Figure 7: Weibull plots of monofilament tensile strength for basalt fibers produced by different manufacturers.

The relationship between Al₂O₃ content and Weibull modulus is shown in Figure 8. Weibull modulus is increased with the increasing of Al₂O₃ content, indicating the basalt fibers with higher Al₂O₃ content have less internal and surface defects and more uniform distribution of defects and strength along the fiber length. We can concluded that improving the content of Al₂O₃ in basalt fibers is beneficial to the uniform distribution of defects along the fiber length, and thus enhance the monofilament tensile strength of fibers.

Figure 8: The relationship between Al₂O₃ content and Weibull modulus of investigated basalt fibers.

3.2.2 Effect of Al₂O₃/Network Former

For the basalt fibers we studied, SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ are glass network formers, Fe₂O₃ plays a dual role and depends on the redox state of iron, FeO, TiO₂, MgO, CaO, Na₂O, K₂O, P₂O₅ and MnO are glass network modifiers. The relationship between the quality ratio of Al₂O₃/network former and monofilament tensile strength of all the investigated basalt fibers are presented in Figure 9. The linear correlation coefficient is 0.86 by fitting the data of Al₂O₃/network former and tensile strength. The tensile strength of basalt fibers are growing linearly with the increasing of Al₂O₃/network former, indicating Al₂O₃ plays a key role in all the glass network formers. In addition, the relationship between Al₂O₃/network former and Weibull modulus is shown in Figure 10. Weibull modulus is also increased with the increasing of Al₂O₃/network former, indicating the basalt fibers with higher Al₂O₃ content in network former have less internal and surface defects and more uniform distribution of defects and strength along the fiber length. Therefore, Al₂O₃ plays a key role in network former of basalt fibers.

Figure 9: Correlation of Al₂O₃/network former and tensile strength of investigated basalt fibers.

Figure 10: The relationship between Al₂O₃/network former and Weibull modulus of investigated basalt fibers.

3.2.3 Effect of Fe³⁺/ΣFe

The redox states of iron has a significant effect on basalt fiber properties such as optical properties, melt viscosity, crystallization behavior, thermal stability, tensile strength and elastic properties. The relationship between Fe³⁺/ΣFe and monofilament tensile strength of all the investigated basalt fibers are shown in Figure 11. The linear correlation coefficient is 0.94 by fitting the data of Fe³⁺/ΣFe and tensile strength. It can be clearly seen that the monofilament tensile strength of basalt fibers are reducing linearly with the increasing of Fe³⁺/ΣFe. In general, to the microstructure, with the increasing of Fe³⁺/ΣFe, more and more Fe³⁺ acts as glass network formers, making the glass network structure more closely connected, thus the monofilament tensile strength of basalt fibers should be larger. But now the opposite is true. There is another key factor that affects the tensile strength of basalt fibers. It is believed that iron cations plays a critical role in the crystallization processes of basalt fiber since an iron-containing spinel phase has lower activation energy of crystallization in comparison with chain and tectosilicates [21]. High content of ferric cations may even cause spontaneous crystallization in a glass melt during fiber formation [22]. Spontaneous crystallization during basalt fiber formation increases defects on the surface of the fibers, and then reducing the tensile strength. In addition, the basalt fibers with high Fe³⁺/ΣFe, there may be more Fe²⁺ converted to Fe³⁺ in the melt, which will release oxygen in the production process and increase the fiber surface defects. It is precisely this phenomenon destroyed the regular pattern of the chemical composition in microstructure.

The relationship between Fe³⁺/ΣFe and Weibull modulus is shown in Figure 12. Weibull modulus is decreased with the increasing of Fe³⁺/ΣFe, indicating the basalt fibers with high Fe³⁺/ΣFe have more internal and surface defects and less uniform distribution of defects and strength along the fiber length. This statement can further confirm the above-mentioned conclusion.

According to the above analysis, it can be concluded that Al₂O₃ content plays a key role in the mechanical properties of basalt fibers, followed by Fe³⁺/ΣFe. Fe³⁺/ΣFe destroyed the regular pattern of the chemical composition in microstructure.

Figure 11: Correlation of $Fe^{3+}/\Sigma Fe$ and tensile strength of investigated basalt fibers.

Figure 12: The relationship between $Fe^{3+}/\Sigma Fe$ and Weibull modulus of investigated basalt fibers.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The relationship between chemical composition and the mechanical properties of seven kinds of basalt fibers producing from different manufacturers were investigated. The results showed that layered structure unit, chain structure unit, island structure unit and Si-Al replacement unit are all existed in basalt fiber microstructure. Al_2O_3 content plays a key role in the mechanical properties of basalt fibers, followed by $Fe^{3+}/\Sigma Fe$. $Fe^{3+}/\Sigma Fe$ destroyed the regular pattern of the chemical composition in microstructure. However, other factors such as melt homogeneity prior to fiber spinning and chemical variation of the samples should be taken into account when evaluating the mechanical properties of basalt fibers in the future.

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